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A Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra (Vedic altruism) based telemedicine network program for rural health care in India

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Abstract: In this post-covid19 era, there is an immense need for telemedicine care for rural people of the developing world including India. Through telemedicine care, novel digital therapeutic devices may be operated to provide rural health care, specially bio-social care. Here, we are reviewing a new public health approach that combines the ancient bio-social medical approach of the Indian Knowledge System with modern medical digital health devices. We have done a two-decade-long research on a piece of the Indian Knowledge System, the Vedic Jiva (living being) Upakara (altruism) Cikitsa (Medical) Tantra (system of knowledge) or Vedic altruism, a near-extinct mind-body-based bio-social medicine approach used in the rural communities of Kamrup, Assam, India. The key metaphysic is the “Avatar”, a Vedic Sanskrit term meaning the emergence (bhava) of a higher being to provide altruistic support to the community under immense stress. Thus the Vedic altruism based public health approach is based on Avatar Kosha, a transient, latent kosha (meaning “sheath” in Sanskrit) that appears only in times of high stress. As per the metaphysics, during stressful times such as epidemic or pandemic, the Avatar Kosha takes on a powerful healing role over the Pancha Kosha system (the five layers of mind-body that surround the Atman (Self) as per Ayurveda) to return the mind-body to homeostasis. Based on this metaphysics, the tantric practitioners of rural Kamrup organized a network of local temple-based healing systems to activate “Avatar Kosha” in the community to combat diseases such as smallpox, cancer, and tuberculosis. The bio-social healing system is a combination of Nigudah yoga-pranayama (yoga focused on breathing), herbal nutrition, and group kirtan chanting in a coordinated manner among the temple networks to induce Sahasa-ojash, a mind-body subtle energy capable of activating the dormant “Avatar Kosha”. Our phenomenological ethnographic research approach indicates that the Avatar Kosha-based healing may have been an indigenous bio-social healing method. In this review paper, we attempt to describe the historical root of the Vedic Altruism-based public health care approach, and our effort to use standard clinical scales such as SF-36, and self-efficacy scale to develop a clinical score to measure Sahasa-Ojash. We also discuss a digital therapeutic device that we found to provide bio-social medical care to a group of patients of the temple complex. We further propose that Vedic Altruism provides the philosophical foundation for what we define as Adaptive Altruism, a stress-induced protective state that can be studied across biological, clinical, and community systems. This review may stimulate health policymakers to give a new look at indigenous methods of bio-social healing. Understanding the metaphysics behind such methods may help us develop novel telemedicine-based digital therapeutic devices for bio-social healing.

Key words: Vedic altruism, telemedicine, Rural Health, Bio-Social Medicine, Indigenous Knowledge System, Cancer, pulmonary tuberculosis, covid-19, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)

Abbreviations: Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT), Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS), Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN), KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care (KTC), and more in page 35
English meaning of various Sanskrit terms used in the text are given in the Glossary, pages 33-3

1.0 Introduction:

A robust rural public health approach is an important element for ensuring productive rural health development. However, the current rural health approach proved to be inadequate in controlling the rise of tuberculosis (TB), cancer and the pandemic of Covid-19. Based on our nearly three decades of participatory action research (PAR) initiative in rural Assam of India through the KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care, we are proposing a new public health approach that combines the ancient ideas of the Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) of Assam and modern medical care to develop a novel model of rural health care system (1,2). This IKS-inspired approach is based on the Jiva Upakara Cikitsa Tantra or Vedic altruism, which is a public health approach having a biosocial medicine component (1,2). Interestingly, biosocial medicine is a rapidly growing field in modern medicine having a particularly significant importance to the post Covid-19 world(3).

For years, our rural clinical team of KTC has been utilizing this Vedic altruism-based biosocial medicine approach to manage chronic lung diseases including chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD), pulmonary tuberculosis (TB), and cancer related lung diseases (4,5). While managing PTB subjects in rural India through the KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care (KTC) (6-9), we have serendipitously discovered the strength of Vedic altruism based philosophy of medicine (1,4), and its possible application in rural tele-health, a rapidly emerging field in rural health (10). Notably, we have uncovered an IKS-based aerosol-inoculation practice reported by British colonial administration (11,12) that demonstrates the possibility of the emergence of herd immunity against tuberculosis (TB), a key element of the social medicine approach against the pathogen (4). We have also uncovered an indigenous Kamarupa information network (IKIN) prevalent in the rural Kamarupa (13), which served as a social capital for the IKS mediated trade along the Vedic Silk Road (Figure 1). These findings require further research and therefore, here we review the concept of Vedic altruism, and its application in telemedicine-based affordable rural health care.

2.0 Vedic altruism-based indigenous medical system of Kamarupa, Assam, India

An Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) is an adaptable knowledge system that is created and maintained by an indigenous culture over many generations. It is receptive to changes in its environment, and thus, becomes capable of producing new knowledge through interactions that take place within the community (14, 15). In India, since the era of Indus valley civilization, tantra (esoteric tradition of yoga philosophy that emphasize mantra and subtle body chakras) may have been a vibrant culture as evident from numerous seals including pashupati seal (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Religion_of_the_Indus_Valley_civilization). Tantric healing methods were an integral part of ancient Indian medicine (11), and may have been used for public health (2). We have proposed a theory of the Cultural Emergence process that predicts that IKS network deep

buried in history may re-emerge in the era of globalization through the process of social networking and knowledge emergence. Harnessing such IKS, and transforming their philosophy into scientific experiments may benefit mankind. Accordingly, applying the participatory action research (PAC) through a rural medical clinic, the KaviKrishna Medical Care, between 1994-2000, we have harnessed the IKS of the weaving and artisan or Shudra community of Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex of rural Kamrup, a district of Assam, the northern eastern state of India (1,2). This effort led us to recover almost the extinct, Vedic Jiva Upakara Cikitsa Tantra, in short Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT) that could translated to English as Vedic Altruism, as the tantra prescribes an altruistic mechanism of healing probably originated during the Vedic age in Kamarupa, Assam (the Sunga-period, 200 BC-100 AD; <https://assamtribune.com/scripts/details.asp?id=may1109/City8>).

Figure 1: Jiva Upakara Tantra based Nigudah Yoga care along the Vedic Silk Route. The Vedic silk route stretched from Kashgar to Cambodia (34). The research about the road was detailed in pages 115-444 of Reference 2. Along the Vedic Silk route, ancient temple complex networks were located, and served as public health centers in Central Asia, Tibet, India, and South Asia during 5th to 12th century (1,2) including some probable surviving neolithic sites of North East India

(Figure 2). In these temple complex networks, JUT healers practiced secret tantric practices including the Nigudah Yoga Pranayama (Nigudah Yoga with a focus on breathing), kirtan chanting, and herbal nutritions to foster a social medicine approach (known as Nigudah yoga care) meant to transfer the bio-social healing effect of Sahasa-ojash from healers to patients, so that the Avatar Kosha can be activated in the patient's mind-body through Nadi (Figure 3). Nigudah yoga is explained here <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9jphxniVOD0>

Jiva Upakara Cikitsa Tantra (JUT) henceforth known as Vedic Altruism, is a notable example of a public health approach that stems from an IKS system of the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex of rural Kamrup district, Assam (13, 14, 16).

Our ongoing research suggests that the IKS origins lie in the ancient Satvata Tantra tradition, one of the earliest Pancharatra tantras, practiced in the 6th century Hayagriva temple of Hajo (Ref 1, Chapter 5.3.12, page 207). Likely, JUT was widely practiced in Hindu temples and Buddhist monasteries during ancient times along the Vedic Silk route that stretched from Central Asia to Cambodia (Figure 1). This indigenous medical practice probably centered around the 6th-century temple of Hayagriva-Madhava temple of Hajo (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hayagriva_Madhava_Temple) as per Bhutanese pilgrimage. This assumption is supported by evidence that some aspects of the tantra such as the energy channels are proto-Hevajra tantra of Heruka (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hevajra>), and Matsayndranath's (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Matsyendranatha>) Akula-vira tantra (<https://shivashakti.com/akulavira>). These two influential tantras, the Hevajra and Akulavira are thought to be composed in Kamarupa after 6th century AD (Suhas Chatterjee (1998), *Indian Civilization and Culture*, P.441, [M D Publications, New Delhi, India](#) (1998)). Moreover, key concept of JUT including Avatarvada and Vyuha manifestations of Vishnu has similarities with the Vedic age movement of Bhagavatism, and Pancharatra-agama. Interestingly, mention of Bhagavatah-valabhadra in a 400 AD inscription of Kamarupa (Umachal inscription, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Umachal_rock_inscription) indicates the presence of Pancharata movement (<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Pancharatra>) in ancient Assam. JUT emphasizes in Bhagavatah, and Vyuha sutra of Pancharatra tantra, which is recited until now at the Hayagriva-Madhava temple of Hajo, indicating the possible Vedic age root of JUT. Furthermore, probable mention of muga silk weaving in the Arthashastra, a ~200 BC text (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arthashastra>) also indicates that Kamrupa was an integral part of the Vedic age movement, and tantra probably originated from the Vratya movement of this era (pages 176-230, reference 1). The synthesis of JUT and other oral traditions with traditional tantras such as Hevajra-tantra and Yogini-tantra probably evolved during the Pala dynasty of Kamarupa through the 8th-10th centuries (Figure 1-2; Ref 1,2). The practice of the oral tradition of JUT went near extinction during 19th century's colonialism (1), and palm-leaf manuscripts are lost, or not yet found. Our research during 1994-1998 showed that only in the Lhuntse part of Eastern Bhutan, and the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex, JUT was preserved as a part of ancient Kamrup's knowledge system among very secret tantric healers (2). Here we shall discuss the practice of JUT or Vedic altruism in rural Kamrup, Assam.

2.1 The practice of Vedic altruism-based bio-social healing in Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex of rural Kamrup, Assam

In the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex of Kamrup district, Assam, India, JUT's teachings were mostly transmitted orally, via surviving practitioners who mainly belong to the Silk-weaving and fisherman community of Vaishnava Hindu sect (1,4). The oral tradition refer to the Suad Muni legend, a legendary Yogi who practiced Avatar-kosha-based medicine, and had miraculous healing powers. Suad Muni Ashram located in the riverbank of Sualkuchi (Figure 2), where tantric healers including Jagat Ghora frequented in search of sacred herbs, soils as well as fecal extracts of tigers, and birds. Our ongoing research indicates that some of the JUT healers spread an orally transmitted form of the Hevajra tantra in the Suad Muni ashram of ancient Sualkuchi (Figure 2). Hevajra tantra is an ancient Kamarupa tantra that greatly influenced tantric Buddhism, and this tantra may have originated from JUT and similar oral tantric traditions (1). Furthermore, JUT healer Jagat Ghora recited Apabhramsa (non-sanskrit linguistic structure) form of Rig Vedic chant suggesting a possible Vatra root of JUT (Ref 1, Chapter 5). Though JUT has deep historical roots as detailed elsewhere (Chapter 5, Ref 1), its practitioners, the local ojhas, kept the tantric-healing methods confidential as per the ancient norms of secrecy (11), and thus, the philosophy nearly went extinct.

In the JUT or Vedic altruism based tantric healing method, the healing practitioners ojhas would use the JUT teachings and methods (Figure 1-3) to manage smallpox, as well as various other ailments believed to be caused by both perceptible and imperceptible types of krimis (microscopic worms akin to the metaphysical creatures mentioned in the Rigveda, Atharvaveda, and Jain sacred texts) (1,2,4). The treatment approach involved using special tantric rituals to control the behavior of krimis. Community-based healing in the form of Nam kirtan (chanting yoga) based air-inoculation, along with herbal extract, and an ancient crude method of blood-based inoculation treatment (12) resembling a basic form of modern plasma therapy (17, 22), were all a part of the approach (1,4). They also used fecal materials, and decomposed plants and soil found in numerous caves of Suad Muni ashram (Figure 2). Importantly, they prepared herbal extracts from more than 36 plants that they harvested in and around the Suad muni ashram, and the cow pasture south of historic tantipara (weaver colony) located south of Hatisatra of Sualkuchi. The urine and feces of cows fed in the pasture filled with the herbs were used for various ailments. Moreover, chanting, and Nigudah yoga treatment was orchestrated as a community medical care model among the temples in the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex. The goal of the community healing process involved the activation of the Sahasa-ojash, which then activates Avatar Kosha and vice versa (Figure 3).

Figure 2. The Archeological site of JUT practice: Suad Muni Ashram along the Vedic Silk Road. **A.** The remnant of the ancient Vedic Silk Road (red arrow) that reach the Bagheswari hill of Sualkuchi. Tantric of Bhutan, Tibet and Central Asia visited this site to pay homage to Mahamuni. The red arrow point to the site of Kavi Krishna Xeel or Rock; yellow arrow point to the Suad muni cave, and white arrow at the top of the hill point to a massive rock, the Garuda rock worshipped by Sun worshipper. Bhutan's tantric pilgrimage used to walk from a similar rock located at the top of Hajo's Garuda pahar to this rock as a part of Garuda tantric ritual. A flat land north of the rock is site of an old Xasang, or a primitive Satra where Madhav Mahanta of Hatisatra lived for 40 years, 1920-1960. In an around the Xasang, about 12 caves and sites are located frequented by tantric healers for their secret gathering at night. The hill is located south to the ancient pond and Shiva temple build by Dharma Pala of 10th century, Shridheswar pukhuri and Sridheswar temple. **B.** Suad muni cave, the site for the preparation of crude vaccination with buffalo blood and herbal extracts, as well as copper beads with muga silk thread. The arrow point to the insert showing a hole on the floor, where tantric JG prepared his herbal paste for the index TB patient (details in the text). **C.** Kavi Krishna xeel visited by the chairman of the department of Tourism, Assam Government. Co-authors T.B., R.D. and S.B. Pilgrimage of Bhutan used to chant while standing on this xeel. The xeel was part of the Kavi Krishna Xasang, where JUT practitioner did river and sun worship. **D.** A brass metal cymbal, and sacred palm-leaves manuscript texts of Mantra were used during kirtan at the Xasang. Some of these sacred "Sanchipat" or palm-leaf texts are supposed to be preserved at the local Hati Satra Temple. The temple owns most of the land in the hill premise. In the photo, a sacred Mantra text postulated to be of Jiva Upakara Tantra, was found in a remote village of Golaghat by study co-author L.P. The sacred "Sanchipat" palm-leaves text is now preserved at Kavi Krishna Laboratory for future research. Photos by S.B. and S.D.

One of the unique methods of JUT based healing was the practice of Satavata-tarka by the healer; through the tarka method healer engaged with the “bad nigudah” or the “ghost” of the “mahamari” (epidemic). The satavata-tarka, and its various aspects are discussed elsewhere (Supplementary note, page 70-85, Reference 4). In this manner, a crude public health approach managed local epidemics. As a part of the Avatar Kosha based practice, inoculation was done by blood taken from sacrificed animals infected with a bad-nigudah (akin to krimis) (Figure 2, Reference 1 & 4 and 17). For example, secretion from smallpox lesions (bad-nigudah) was injected into a buffalo a few months before it was sacrificed to the Goddess Kamakhya. Then, the buffalo blood was used to inoculate people during a smallpox epidemic (Figure 2; Ref 1 & 17). The inoculation against smallpox became popular and was even mentioned by the colonial British administration of Assam (12,17,22).

2.2 Metaphysics of Vedic Altruism and its modern relevance in the philosophy of medicine:

This ancient cikitsa (medicinal) tantra has modern relevance because of the underlying metaphysics of global health (1,4). According to JUT, life on earth generally exists as a conflict between Prakriti (Nature) and the harmful krimis residing in the atmosphere, mountains, and rivers that try to destroy Prakriti (Chapter 1&2, Ref. 1). Prakriti exerts bio-defense to maintain life in Earth, through the process of Madhu-vidya. This metaphysics inspired the cover of a book written by BD, the Science Behind Squalene (23). The bio-defense is a key concept of JUT, and the healing is considered as an act of defense by the Pancha-kosha system, including nigudahs (smallest unit of life found in our body), and this concept inspired the idea of the stem cell niche defense depicted in the Figure 14 of the book, the Science Behind Squalene (23), as well as the idea of stem cell altruism (background part of the press release, <https://www.eurekalert.org/news-releases/696977>).

A key metaphysics of JUT involves the Vidhata-ojash, a putative, altruistic social defense mechanism that is triggered during times of environmental stress due to the harmful nigudahs (nigoda) or krimis (microscopic life forms as per Vedic and Jain scriptures; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nigoda>). From the Vidhata-ojash's activation, the Vidhatha Kshetra, (an Avatar of the biofield/environment) transiently emerges to destroy the harmful krimis, thereby protecting Prakriti through altruistic behavior (Chapter 2.7, page 80-86, Ref. 1). Thus, JUT presents an innovative metaphysics of global health defense against the environmental stress. The metaphysics of JUT is probably an early and crude version of Vedantic Philosophical theory of altruistic behavior of inner self as mentioned in the poem "Fire of Golden Nail" written by poet Krishna Ram Das, a Vedic philosopher poet of Sualkuchi. The Vedantic view on altruism greatly differ from Darwinian altruism in the sense that during stress, the living organism acquires a higher state, known as 'Avatar', which probably influenced local tantric of Kamarupa's healing practice.

Figure 3: The Yantra (instrument based on a manasa Kuttaka or mind based algorithm) of healing instrument of Jiva Upakara Tantra based Nigudah care. The holistic interaction between Dhata (self-efficacy/self-reliance) and community collaboration network (Nadi) led to the emergence of Shasa-ojash, a bio-social healing force that enhances individual quality of life. The main concept and innovation of JUT is the Avatar Kosha, a transient kosha that emerges when the two distinct entities interact during stress such as sickness. In the case of this figure, the two entities are the patient and his/her healer, represented by the idea of a yantra (a geometrical, complex healer's instrument) that activates Avatar Kosha. Both the healer and patient interact in a kshetra (field) known as svatantrasthan in the subtle or virtual world. This interaction or dialect leads to the connection of their ojashes to form the Nadi (channel), which in turn leads to the emergence of a wisdom or knowledge called Vak-Bubudhan Prajna. The shakti (power) of this Prajna (wisdom) activates the systems of the body, and from that, the Vak-Vidhata Avatar Kosha and Sahasa-Ojash emerge, strengthening the Vyadhikhamatva. This then improves the patient's Budhanna Dhata (awakened self) (Rig Veda 7.68.9). This form of yantra may be an integral part of tantra and tantric healing (11). The Yantra propose a process of knowledge emergence (Prajna Agan) practiced by local education system of silk weaver and other artisans (24). The figure is the copy of Figure 1, Ref 1, Chapter 2.1, page 31. Due permission is taken from the publisher.

Analogous to JUT's metaphysic global health concept is JUT's concept of the metaphysics of individual health (Figure 3). An individual's Avatar Kosha arises through an interaction between a yantra (a complex healer's instrument), the patient and his/her healer through their combined Nadi (energy network). Through this interaction, the bad-nigudah can be transformed in the Svatantra kshetra (a more independent, stronger version of Vidhata Kshetra) to become good-nigudah (Figure 4 in Ref 4), which then activates a transient Avatar Kosha in the inner layer of the Pancha kosha system. The emergence of Avatar Kosha will potently increase the flow of Sahasa-ojash, leading to the activation of Vyadhikshamatva (Figure 3), the immune system of the body as per Ayurveda (18-21). As a result, all the bad-nigudah will transform into good-nigudah, and the person will then be able to spread this good-nigudah to their community (Figure 1 of Ref 4). This idea of the transformative power of Avatar Kosha stem from the Vyhua sutra and Madhu Vidya of Vedimetaphysics related to social buffering against stress. (Chapter 2, Ref.1). The transformation involves the activation of a powerful self-esteem image of healing, the "Sahasa-Ojash" in the mind of a patient by an able healer or Sadhak, so that the patient's Avatar-Kosha can be activated (Figure 3). At the heart of the Avatar kosha practice was a breathing yoga, the Nigudah Yoga (https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=128555009421171&id=109061731370499; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9jphxniVQD0>), proper nutrition including local herbs, and a self-care practice called Shraddha.

For the Avatar-kosha to be effective in the community, a temple network is required, and thus, many of the temples of Sualkuchi-Hajo area were incorporated into this network, the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN).

2.3 Adaptive Altruism: scientific translation of Vedic Altruism

The concept of Vedic Altruism may also be understood through the emerging biological framework of Adaptive Altruism. We define Adaptive Altruism as a stress-induced protective state in which a living system transiently reorganizes itself to defend a larger biological or social whole. In this framework, altruism is not viewed merely as a moral virtue, emotional compassion, or self-sacrifice; rather, it is an adaptive response that emerges during crisis, when a cell, tissue, organism, healer-patient dyad, community, or ecological network acquires a higher protective capacity and uses that capacity to restore homeostasis.

This idea closely parallels the JUT concept of Avatar Kosha, in which a higher protective state emerges during periods of injury, infection, social disruption, or environmental threat to restore balance and strengthen Vyadhikshamatva. In modern biological terms, similar stress-induced protective responses may be observed in stem-cell niches, immune regulation, host-pathogen interactions, tissue repair, and community-level resilience. Thus, Vedic Altruism provides a civilizational and metaphysical language for a phenomenon that modern biology is beginning to recognize as adaptive, relational, and system-protective.

We incorporated this concept into our science by translating the metaphysics of Vedic Altruism/Jiva Upakara Tantra into experimentally testable models. The JUT concept of Avatar Kosha guided our thinking on stress-induced stem-cell states, stem-cell niche defense, and altruistic stem cells that protect tissues under pathological stress. Similarly, the good-nigudah concept helped us design studies on host–pathogen interaction in tuberculosis, including the search for protective extracellular vesicle–mediated mechanisms. At the clinical and community level, KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care incorporated Adaptive Altruism through biosocial care, where self-care, healer–patient interaction, digital follow-up, community collaboration, and Sahasa-ojash measurement are used to strengthen resilience among rural patients with tuberculosis, cancer, COPD, and Covid-19. Thus, Adaptive Altruism provides the scientific bridge between Vedic Altruism, stem-cell biology, host defense, and community-based global health.

3. 0 Guided interaction between Vedic Altruism based healing method and modern medical practice:

How do we integrate IKS-based healing methods with Western medical practice for the evolution of an integrated modern medical system which is people centric, and reduces health disparity of rural world? We took a participatory action research (PAR) approach through the primary care clinic, the KaviKrishna Medical Care of Sualkuchi (now evolved as the KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care) to address the issue of integration so that we do not exploit or appropriate the IKS as was done during colonialism, but, instead, enhance and keep the identity of the IKS intact, plus recognition it's contribution to our scientific growth. In this context, as outlined below, through this section 3, we made tremendous progress during 1994-2022 to integrate these two different systems of medical care approach to develop clinical and biomedical research programs, plus the idea and operation on a telemedicine network based on the metaphysics of Vedic altruism based biosocial healing.

From 1993 to 1994, during his early years of primary clinical practice, BD observed rural tantric healer Jagat Ghora (JG)"s JUT-based aerosol-inoculation approach against tuberculosis (1,4,17). JG"s patients with pulmonary TB (PTB) were asked to perform kirtan chanting in Hatisatra namghar (a local temple in Sualkuchi; the birthplace of the KaviKrishna laboratory) to transmit good-nigudahs around the community. BD had direct conflict with the tantric JG, as he believed such actions were dangerously spreading TB, and thus a dialogue of focused group discussion (FGD) between BD and JG"s teams was conducted as detailed elsewhere (Supplementary note of Ref 4). Upon discussing, BD speculated that a convergence of the ideas behind Kamrup"s IKS and with those of modern medical practice may materialize novel insight about disease pathology (23). Furthermore, considering the rich tradition of knowledge generation-based culture in ancient India (24,25), BD took JG"s metaphysical view of treatment seriously. Therefore, BD aimed to first conceptualize good-Nigudah of aerosol-inoculation, and then study its potential rationale using modern

laboratory-based methods (Figure 4 of Ref 4). BD's team ultimately succeeded in formulating the metaphysics behind JG's good-nigudah based aerosol-inoculation against PTB, as shown in Figure 4, and detailed in the supplementary note of Ref 4. Subsequently, the spread of bad-nigudah aerosols from other PTB subjects is combatted by the good-nigudah, which provides protection to the community. In JUT, the hypothesis of "Nigudah-immunity" describes the body defense mechanism of good-nigudah (Figure 1A, Reference 4). When discussing these concepts with JG, we suggested that sputum positive pulmonary TB subjects (these subjects are capable of transmitting TB through aerosols) should not be included in his kirtan yoga practices inside a temple complex since bacteria reside in the sputum of smear positive pulmonary TB subjects. As a trade-off, we agreed to conduct a contact TB investigation study among the kirtan chanters, as per suggestion by JG and the Vedic Philosopher, Krishna Ram Das, the then patron of KaviKrishna trust (34) and an expert in the metaphysics of Vedic Altruism (35). They suggested us to design experiments for the potential findings of good-nigudah. Through JUT's method of tarka, an investigative method of suppositional reasoning (25), an experimental design of a contact TB investigation study made with the aim of testing the "nigudah-immunity" hypothesis (Figure 4, Ref 4), and finally led to the discovery of a new stem cell mediated aerosol-based herd immunity against TB (4).

As outlined below, we have done numerous clinical research following appropriate ethical permission through our institutional ethics committee as well as the institutional ethics committee of our collaborative institutions such as Guwahati Medical College & Hospital, Gauhati University, Jawaharlal Nehru University, and Indian Institute of Technology-Guwahati of India, as well as Forsyth Institute of Cambridge, USA, and the Stanford University of California. The results of these pilot clinical studies are either being published or being under preparation for submissions. Thus, an unique process of participatory action research (PAR) approach centered around KaviKrishna organization of Sualkuchi has started to take shape during our relentless work between 1994 through 2022. The PAR process started with a humble beginning during 1994-2000, when BD's clinical primary care practice at KaviKrishna Medical Care (another name, Micro clinic of Sualkuchi) of Kamrup (evolved as KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care since 2004) and Mongar Hospital of Bhutan started integrating the metaphysics components of Vedic altruism to develop a research program with the core idea of studying the oxidative stress component of disease pathogenesis as mentioned in the part-1 of the book, the Science Behind Squalene published in the year 2000 (23). The core theme of the book is the role of antioxidant supplements such as squalene in keeping our body healthy. This idea and passion came to BD's mind, during the early period of PAR, as BD incorporated the nutritional and yoga components of Vedic altruism, such as whey protein supplements, selected herbal extracts rich in Squalene and other anti-oxidants, as well as the

Nigudah yoga. Importantly, as mentioned in the Figure 14 of the book, the idea of the stem cell niche defense, and the subsequent idea of stem cell altruism based defense stem from the unique metaphysics of Vedic altruism based biosphere defense as discussed in details in the subsequent book, KaviKrishna Laboratory, *Recovering the spirit of Jiva Upakara Tantra* published in the year 2019 (1). The idea and evidences on the stem cell niche defense is now the hard-core of KaviKrishna Laboratory and Thoreau Laboratory's biomedical research program in understanding the fundamental pathogenesis of cancer, infectious diseases such as TB, as well as possible impact of pollution and climate change in human body. Taken together, these works, spanning nearly three decades now provide the foundation of a new and unique process of PAR for rural India's primary care practice-based research.

3.1 IKS-based Contact TB investigation:

In the field of contact investigation study of TB, one valuable method of case-findings to study the disease transmission process is examination of close family and social contact of index cases at the time of diagnosis (26). As an example, we selected a 32-year-old male from the south-west region of Sualkuchi as an index case of sputum positive pulmonary or lung TB. The local Namghar (temple), Ishwar Shree Shree Hati Satra (<https://www.facebook.com/hatisatra/?rf=82387327776650>), had many devotee and practitioners of kirtan-yoga-chanting who were in contact with the TB index case. For the initial 5 years (1994-1999), we incorporated 110 of the temple devotees for contact TB tracing study. Out of 75 subjects who participated in regular kirtan chanting once a day for one hour, on average, 3 (4%) were sputum negative- pulmonary TB subjects (not under regular treatment) and 20 (26%) were in close contact with the index subject. Another group of 35 people who were not attending kirtan chanting were found to be in close contact with the index subject. In our analysis, we compared the prevalence of pulmonary TB among these kirtan-chanting (n=20) and non-kirtan chanting groups (n=35), all of whom were in close contact with the index case. After 5 years, 0/20 of the kirtan chanting group was infected with pulmonary TB, compared to 3/35 of the non-kirtan chanting group (Figure 2, Reference 4). During the next 15 years (1994-2009) of follow up, the data showed that none of the index case exposed subjects attending regular kirtan chanting became infected with pulmonary TB (Figure 3A & B, Reference 4). Yet, there was a 9% chance of infection with pulmonary TB among the exposed subjects who did not attend kirtan chanting, a percentage that is consistent with national data on contact-tracing (27). This data is a preliminary result from a small sample size, and therefore has limited use for drawing definitive conclusions. However, its findings encouraged us to conduct another FGD of tarka to model good-

nigudah, which is described below.

Figure 4: Formulation of the metaphysics behind good-nigudah based aerosol-inoculation against PTB.

Nigudah krimis (invisible krimis as per Ayurveda), known as nigudah in the Jain sacred texts, can cause illness in a person when the number of good (Upakari or sahaja or suad) nigudah decline in comparison to the

number of bad (Apakari or piscacha) nigudah, due to weakness in Nigudah-immunity (4). A tantric healer or ojah tries to tilt this imbalance by activating the Avatar Kosha by providing nigudah yoga care, as well as crude inoculation (17). Activated Avatar Kosha in turn activates Vyadhikshaymatva of the pancha-kosha of the patient (Figure 3). Avatar Kosha sacrifices its healing power in extracting good-nigudah from bad-nigudah and in the process enhances fitness or power of the pancha-koshas of patient's body. Increasing levels of good-nigudah lead to a quick recovery and enhancement of the Sahaja JivaOjas, or the innate bio-energy of patient's body which then enhances Sahasa-ojash (details in pages 8-19, Reference 1). After the person recovers, the tantric healers or ojahs employ the recovering patient having activated Avatar Kosha to spread good-nigudah via aerosol-inoculation within the community. As a consequence, the bad-nigudah of sick patients (broken red arrow) cannot spread within the community. Final result is the increase of Vyadhikshaymatva of the entire community leading to prevention and control of TB. Vyadhikshaymatva meaning immune defense mechanism, (18-21) is an Ayurvedic concept that the metaphysics of Sahasa-Ojash is based on. The figure is the copy of Figure 1, Ref 4 bioRxiv with due permission. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.11.14.382572>.

3.2 Metaphysics based modeling of good-nigudah led to the isolation of antigen rich extracellular vesicles in the aerosols of pulmonary TB patients:

Knowledge emergence, a network process of interaction among the practitioners of local indigenous knowledge and practical philosophy (14,24) can substantiate the challenging process of deriving of a scientific

hypothesis from metaphysical concepts (28). Satvata tarka, the JUT dialectic approach of interaction and reasoning, may lead to knowledge emergence (Chapter 2.2, pages 42-47, Reference 1). To analyze the results of the contact investigation study, we carried out another Satvata tarka based FGD as per the JUT tradition in 2009 (Figure 4A, and supplementary note 1, Reference 4). The aim of this session was to formulate an experimental design that would allow for identification of the putative good-nigudahs from the sputum negative pulmonary TB subjects. In the FGD session, the dialectic of Satvata tarka (Figure 4A, and Supplementary note 1, Reference 4) was implemented to discuss two seemingly opposite interpretations of the results of the contact-investigation study. BD's interpretation was as follows: through kirtan chanting, sputum negative pulmonary TB subjects might have internalized bad-nigudah, to which their body's immune system responded, neutralizing the bad-nigudah and creating immunity. Alternatively, Vedic philosopher Dayal Krishna Bora (DKB)'s interpretation was as follows: through kirtan chanting, sputum negative pulmonary TB subjects might have spread good components of bad bacteria as good-nigudah, leading to the spread of immunity against the pathogen (Nigudah-immunity, Figure 1A, and Figure 4A, Reference 4). Though their opinions opposed one another, this FGD sparked curiosity in BD to look further into the possibility of a scientific explanation for DKB's claims. In the third FGD session, DKB applied a JUT based theory of reflection (Upakar Pratibimbawada, page 66, Ref 4, and page 110, Ref 1) to conceptualized the structure of a hypothetical good-nigudah inside the TB bacteria as an extracellular vesicle (Figure 4B, Ref. 4). These FGD sessions ultimately led to the conceptualization of an experimental design and eventual findings of Mtb-antigens residing in extracellular vesicles (EV) (Figure 5-9, Ref 4). Satvata tarka effectively provoked knowledge emergence through which these Mtb-antigens (possibly visualized as good-nigudah) were identified (Figure 9, Ref 4). Importantly, nearly two decades long contact investigation study facilitated the continuity of the KaviKrishna telemedicine care (Chapter 4.5, page 160, Ref 1). Next, we utilized the resources of KTC to perform a social network (Figure 1-3, Ref. 14) based management of cancer disparity of n=150 subjects between 2010-2019 (Ref. 13, and a manuscript under preparation for submission) and estimated the induction of Avatar Kosha through quantifying the sahasa-ojash by standard clinical instruments that we use in our clinical practice as described below and detailed in Ref 1 and 13.

3.3. Use of modern clinically validated instruments to measure Shasa-ojash

We have developed a clinical scale to evaluate the effectiveness of Avatar-kosha therapy on patients—the Sahasa-ojash, which could be defined as a combination of;

- good physical and mental health (Anna maya, prana maya, and monomoya kosha),
- high level of self-esteem (Vigyan moaya kosha),
- and, the ability to collaborate with community members for a given social cause without having anxiety (healthy interacton between Mono moya, Vigyan moya and Ananda moaya kosha)

Each of these dimensions of Sahasa-ojash were approximated and measured by validated clinical instruments.

Table 1: Assigning equivalent validated instruments to measure Avatar-kosha functional equivalents.

Aspect of Patient well-being measured	Avatar-kosha functional equivalent	Modern medical standard of measure employed by KKL
Physical and Mental Health	Anna maya, prana maya, and monomoya kosha	SF-36: Short form 36 Quality of Life Survey
Self-esteem	Vigyan moya kosha	Rosenberg’s self-esteem scale
Collaborative Skill	Mono moya, Vigyan moya and Ananda moaya kosha	Self-assessed collaboration skill (SACS)
Anxiety	Prana moya, Mono maya and Vigyan moaya kosha	Hamilton Anxiety Scale

Figure 5: Measuring Avatar kosha on cancer patient by Sahasa-ojash scoring. The Sahasa-ojash scale is the ratio between the self-efficacy (measured by self-efficacy scale and HRQOL that measure Dhata) and collaboration survey (measured during focused group discussion, and their collaboration with the KTC team; this measures the Nadi, Figure 3). Nigudah yoga care involved telemedicine-based discussions each Saturday, and the patients participate in self-care as suggested by us, including Nigudah yoga, steam inhalation/good nutrition/ whey protein supplements for cancer patients. The Sahasa-ojash scale is under development and not yet fully validated. In the lymphoma patients for the lymphoma research project (7), the average score was: 35 for HRQOL-35, 15 for Self-esteem, 3 for SACS 0-7, 25 for Hamilton scale. The data is shown in Figure 5D. SACS 0-7 score was done as described previously (Hinyard L et al. 2019, PMID:29334770). HRQOL: Health Related Quality of Life. SACS: self-assessed collaboraton skills; Rosenberg self-esteem scale: <https://www.academia.edu/19813736/>; Hamilton anxiety rating scale: Br J Med Psychol 1959; 32:50–55

We considered the activation of Avatar kosha in a patient if the sahasa-ojash score was equal or more than 5 (Figure 5). Initially, we have applied this sahasa-ojash scale to evaluate the efficacy of Nigudah yoga care in subjects suffering from Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), a growing global health problem. Incidence and prevalence of COPD is growing because of urban pollution, climate change and increase number of elderly patients living in rural household having poor ventilation. We have recruited n=15

people with COPD($FEV_1/FEV_6 < 0.3$, table 1, Ref 4) to evaluate the efficacy of the Nigudah yoga care, and found that five weeks of the care increased the sahasa-ojash scale by 3-fold ($p < 0.001$; Figure 6). The study also demonstrated the close association between poor score of sahasa-ojash and breathlessness (Figure 7). These two initial studies led us to identify a dormant indigenous kamarupa information network (IKIN) prevalent among the silk weaver and artisans of crafts related to bell metal, brass metal and pottery of Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex (37,38, 39), Figure 6 A-C. These poor artisans were given free medical advice by KTC, and were recruited to our health care network through frequent home visit. In the process we became aware of an IKS based indigenous kamarupa information network (IKIN), Figure 6 A-B. Through this IKIN, we did complete two major scientific works on tuberculosis and cancer (5,7), and a major telemedicine based care of $n=1500$ covid19 patients (Figure 6C, Ref. 45,46 and 55). Results of these studies are reviewed below. However, before we review our field study results, we shall briefly discuss the “altruistic” aspect of IKIN based healing effects

3.4. Care of Tuberculosis patients in rural India through Vedic Altruism based telemedicine network approach:

Although not relevant for this discussion, suffice to mention here that we have utilized the metaphysic of Vedic altruism to identify altruistic stem cells (40), and their interaction with *M.tuberculosis* (Background part of Elsevier press release, Ref 41) (9). We have used the KTC based telemedicine care to complete a study on the stem cell basis of tuberculosis funded by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (59). To investigate the bone marrow stem cell niche as the site of *M.tuberculosis* dormancy, we performed a clinical study in the Roing distric of Arunachal Pradesh during the summer of 2010. The clinical study was approved by Stanford Stem Cell Research Oversight Panel, Stanford University (Protocol number 289; Principal Investigator, Bikul Das), RIWATCH (<https://riwatch.in>) of Arunachal Pradesh (RCH/RNG-253/2010; Principal Investigator, Ista Pulo), Institutional Research Ethics Board at the Guwahati Medical College & Hospital (MC/190/2007/1097; Date: 02/03/2010; Principal Investigator: Deep Jyoti Kalita) and KaviKrishna (KKL/2/2010; PI: Bikul Das)

Figure 6: Vedic Altruism based telemedicine care at KTC. *A.* The ancient geometric symbols of Indus valley (55). Similar symbols and seven pipal leaf in a circular form is used by JUT healer during mantra chanting in the Indigenous Kamarupa Information Network (IKIN) of the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex, Kamrup, Assam. The seven concentric circles are used in the Nigudah Yoga practice, and found in the rocks at the top of Dhareswari temple located in Bamundi, one of the member temples of IKIN. *B.* The geographic area of the historical Cikitsha Satra (temple-based public health network) of Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex. KaviKrishna telemedicine care is operating in this area for the last two-and-half-decades. Hindu temples located in these rural area of Kamarupa operated as an unique public health system, where the JUT practioners, and tantric healing practioners of diverse tantra of the area practiced the Vidhatha-Manthan to activate the Vidhatha-kosha (Avatar kosha in the community level) in order to enhance the iccha-shakti (will power) and sahasa-ojash of community members. Hence, the process is equivalent to the bio-social medical practice.. These satra/temple network is now used for our social network analysis to study IKIN mediated Avatar Kosha in a temple network community. To measure the sahasa-ojash of individual practioners during the Vidhata-manthan

practice, we have developed a clinical scale as outlined in Figure 5. The results are analyzed by modern social networking analysis softwares, as shown in C, and detailed in reference 13,42 and 46. C. A social network diagram showing a bridging hub network in the geographic area of (B) activated by KTC during the covid-19 pandemic (42,46) suggesting the emergence of Vidhata Kosha in IKIN. D. Improvement in the Shasaja-ojash scale of patients following weeks of Nigudah yoga care. Details in Ref. 42.

We recruited subjects (n=12 for bone marrow study, and n=26 for the circulating mesenchymal study) from the Idu-Mishmi tribe (5) living in Roing, Arunachal Pradesh, where KaviKrishna has been doing rural telemedicine care since 2010 through Dr. Ista Pulo's clinic. Their area, along with nearby Parashu Ram, has been a part of the Muga silk (traditional, durable silk of Assam) trade route since ancient times. We then engaged the Idu-Mishimi people, as well as the Idu tribe, in several medical camps and recruited some of the tribe members to be patients for our clinical study, and isolating bone marrow as well as circulating mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). We selected people with a previous history of pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) who took the DOTS (directly observed therapy short course) program for TB, and who, for the past two years, have lived a relatively healthy life (although some of them were suffering from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease). In this cohort of n= 12 cases, we performed a magnetic sorting of the CD271+/CD45-/ CD33- fraction in bone marrow (BM). All of the participants gave written, informed consent and were older than 40-years-old. Subjects who had diabetes or heart disease, or were pregnant, were excluded. Previously treated subjects were prospectively recruited based on the local tuberculosis control program data and Chest X-ray findings. Additionally, all participants had routine HIV testing done using Abbott Determine HIV1/2 rapid antibody assay test kit (Abbott Laboratories). Pulmonary TB patients were diagnosed based on sputum and Chest X-ray findings and all subjects with a previous history of sputum AFB (Acid Fast Bacillus) +++, and Chest X-ray showed active cavity formation. Patients were given DOTS II by the local government district hospital.

After the completion of treatment, acid fast bacillus (AFB) and culture of sputum were performed by the Ranbaxy Laboratory, in Mumbai, and were found to be both negative. In addition, no M.tuberculosis-DNA could not be detected in treated patients' sputum, blood and BM aspirates. Healthy control participants were recruited from volunteers between 40-50 years old. We then worked with these patients for two weeks, giving them home visit, and encouraging them to perform breath holding test, steam inhalation, and deep breathing, the component of Nigudah yoga (Figure 1; Ref 42). These patients (n=38) were assessed for the Sahasa-ojash scale (Figure 5), and the result of some of these subjects are included in the results shown in Figure 6D (the COPD and sputum negative PTB groups).

The laboratory results of the presence of viable Mtb intracellular to CD271+ BM-MSCs residing in the bone marrow stem cell niche was published in 2013 (5). The lab results of the n=26 cases are yet to be published as we are observing these cases for possible relapse. Now, we are continuing with the application of the JUT based telemedicine for pulmonary TB cases across North East. Since 2010, we have recruited n=35 pulmonary TB cases of rural Assam for the circulating MSC study, and these subjects were subjected to the Nigudah care for five weeks.

Figure 7: A thematic network analysis of n=35 selected cases of pulmonary TB, cancer and COPD indicates the close link between Sahasa-ojash with breathlessness and anxiety. Focused group discussion through video chat was achieved each week of Nigudah care with the telemedicine team. The patients are from the geographical area of IKIN (Figure 6B). The data taken prior to Nigudah yoga care (week zero in Figure 6D) was subjected to grounded theory-based thematic network analysis as described previously (4). The detail of methodologies and data analysis are given in Ref. 42 (manuscript under preparation).

The cumulative results are shown in Figure 6D (the PTB sputum negative group) which strongly indicate the benefit of Nigudah-yoga care to reduce the chances of relapse, as explained in the discussion part of a review paper recently published (8). Interestingly, the study also demonstrated the close association between poor score of sahasa-ojash and breathlessness (Figure 7) (detailed data are given in Ref. 42).

Recently, following a DBT funded grant, we recruited n=250 TB patients, including MDR-TB, from the entire northeast region for another study to evaluate the efficacy of Nigudah care. In this n=250 population, we are currently applying the Vedic Altruism based telemedicine approach for continuous monitoring for

probable relapse. We are now using a whole genome sequencing (WGS) based surveillance approach to monitor the evolution of MDR TB and evaluate the role of the stem cell niche. The preliminary results indicate that the Vedic altruism based telemedicine approach may be applied as a digital therapeutic tool in TB control program (42).

3.5 Vedic altruism based Digital Therapeutic Device, IKIN:

Since 2018, the KTC has increased the use of digital tools for our patients, and volunteers to help patients utilize them, including videos, internet-access, and computer education (the “*Third-eye Center of Sualkuchi*”). In this manner, we are transforming the IKIN into an online social network-based hybrid digital therapeutic device (DTx). Considering the emerging role of DTx in TB control program in rural India, our future goal is to transform the IKIN (Figure 6B-C) into a hybrid digital therapeutics to translate the National Treatment Elimination Program-based (NTEP – formerly the RNTCP: The Revised National TB Control Programme) prevention and treatment of pulmonary TB (PTB) in rural India (42). A current 5-year prospective cohort study is ongoing, scheduled for completion in June 2023. The study is a quasi-experimental research design including a single-arm pre- and post-intervention measuring body weight, Sputum for AFB/culture, breath-holding test, and program engagement outcome.

The IKIN is a digital therapeutic device (DTx) that provides (42):

- A Weekly Virtual Clinic including health curriculum and monitoring via RNTCP guidelines
- Lifestyle coaching including nutrition/herbal gardening
- Home Spirometry
- Pulse oximetry evaluation
- Weight monitoring
- Focused group discussion (FGD)
- Online Rehabilitation Programs

In line with the Digital Therapeutic Alliances’ definitions, our IKIN DTx encompasses the following DTx tools:

- Digital monitoring of BP, weight, and hemoglobin
- Monitoring of sputum collection and blood via hybrid access through KTC (Figure 6.)
- Focused group discussions
- Weekly telemedicine calls and patient follow-up
- Nigudah Yoga training camp via online classes
- Herbal extracts and drink prepared from the 36-JUT based herbal extract plants._

Focused group discussion allows networking between participants, discussing goal achievement, and participating in events and festivals related to IKIN cultural tradition. *Hybrid evaluation* refers to merging our DTx with real-time lab values of hemoglobin monitoring and sputum collection in the local unit of the KTC. The DTx program offers a core 8-week intensive IKIN-based DTx interaction to participants – and participants are then offered continuation with a post-intensive core therapy of 24 months duration. Our investigators are collecting data and evaluating the Sahasa-ojash scales of this cohort to report upon completion as detailed in reference 42.

3.6 Vedic Altruism based telemedicine network approach for affordable rural cancer care

We have utilized the metaphysic of Vedic altruism based theory of Avatar kosha turning into Asura Kosha (36) or Kala-Ojash (43) to study the transformation of stem cells to cancer stem cells (40; Chapter 4 of Ref 1). The study led to identification of a molecular pathway of stem cell altruism (44), which we identified in cancer stem cells of clinical subjects (7). For these laboratory studies we have recruited cancer patients through KTC, specially a recently concluded study on lymphoma stem cells (7), as well as providing free consultation and palliative care for nearly one thousand rural patients for the last two decades. Our lab has also been working with a rural population from Sualkuchi, Assam, India for 20 years via KTC to evaluate the cancer health disparity in rural India (6). To identify different elements that underlie cancer health disparities, we initiated a longitudinal study in the greater Sualkuchi area. Via KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care, 150 cancer patients from rural Sualkuchi were identified and we proceeded to map out each patient's social network system through regular home and doctor visits, interviews, and focused group discussion. Through these regular focused group meetings, we empowered one group of patients (n=82 of total 150 patients) with basic knowledge about their disease and the available treatments. In 3 month intervals, we then repeated the FGDs with patients and their family to gather data, that was then fed into an IKS-network analysis tool as described previously (13) as to whether the patients communicated their knowledge and experience in such a way that would generate knowledge emergence within the IKS.

The results showed that the patients with evidence of communicating through a pre-existing IKS-based system were positively responding to our care services and group discussions, as they were becoming emotionally and psychologically capable of managing their self-care, as compared to the control population (13). Additionally, the allostatic load (30) of the people in the control group was significantly higher than that of the people in the treatment group (13). Our results indicate that this Vedic Altruism based telemedicine care and its putative Avatar Kosha based healing act as a stress-buffering, as per the stress-buffering hypothesis (31).

3.7 Vedic altruism based telemedicine network approach for the management of Covid-19 patients in rural India:

Awareness of bio-social medicine is growing as a community-based public health service (29). Run through a network of temples, the Nigudah Yoga Pranayama (Nigudah Yoga with a focus on breathing) in combination with nutritional programs foster a social medicine approach (known as Nigudah yoga care) meant to enhance the bio-social healing effect of Sahasa-ojash (Figure 1). KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care (KTC) activated our IKS-based Ckitisha Satra (temple-hospital) network (5, 7, 13, 39) in the first wave of the Covid-19 pandemic to obtain retrospective and prospective data on clinical features of the disease among the local population. In addition, KTC also studied the ICMR guidelines for treating the disease, especially the pulmonary hypoxemia (45, 46). Then, KTC performed a Satvata tarka based FGD between traditional healers that manage lung diseases, local doctors, health workers and rural physician assistants. This guided interaction led to the emergence of a Covid19 specific Nigudah Yoga Pranayama based management for home care patients.

In the anticipation of the second wave, we further strengthened our telemedicine-based Cikitsha Satra network and then, during the 2nd wave of Covid-19, we provided our adapted version of Nigudah Yoga Care plan (45,46) to more than 1500 Covid-19, home-isolated patients (stage I and stage II). This IKS-based care comprises of Nigudah Yoga Pranayama, Bhape-Jala-Kriya (steam inhalation), naka mukha Suddhi (Oral and Nasal hygiene) such as povidone iodine solution, and standard symptomatic treatment of Covid-19. The home-care plan includes the active monitoring of patient oxygen saturation (SPO2), breath-holding test (BHT), respiration rate, temperature, and the timely referral to district Covid-19 Hospitals, if required. The disease progression or recovery was monitored by performing a Nigudah-pulse-oximeter test, which includes 3 oximeter readings throughout the Nigudah yoga process, daily for 30 minutes/3 times (45). The Cikitsha Network team performed the health monitoring parameters in the patients via virtual media. Additionally, a total of 150 pulse oximeters, 3000 pamphlets, 2000 booklets in the local language explaining the home care plan (45), nearly 5000 of Nigudha yoga short video through WhatsApp group and some medications, were distributed among the study subjects following precaution guidelines of ICMR (45,46). We evaluated the effectiveness of the adapted Nigudah Yoga Care in reducing the progression of Covid-19 in the rural population of Kamrup. The results showed a significant effectiveness in reducing the odds of progression of stage IIa to stage IIb/III disease in the anemic as well as non-anemic group (46), suggesting the potential effectiveness of the Vedic Altruism based bio-social medicine approach in managing mild to moderate Covid-19 cases in rural India (46).

4.0 Discussion and limitations of these clinical pilot studies

Nations such as India and China, which have a rich, complex culture stemming from the remains of their ancient civilizations, have intricate Indigenous Knowledge Systems that continue to thrive as undisclosed public knowledge (UPK) of public health importance (14, 23). We speculated that the IKS based health care can be implemented in rural population as a part of global health efforts in this era of climate change and pandemic. Our two decades of experiences with a IKS based tele-health approach indicates the potential benefit of rural tele-health.

A robust rural public health approach is an integral element of rural health development. The general health of the people in rural populations is inferior to that of urban populations (47); rural areas tend to have shorter life expectancy and high mortality rates due to infectious diseases like tuberculosis (TB) and other deadly diseases, such as cancer (48). Despite these adverse statistics, while 72.2% of Indian people reside in rural areas, only 40.8% of healthcare workers are available for rural areas (4). Thus, it is imperative that the public health management of rural populations in developing countries, such as India, improves.

Currently, the rural health care system of India consists of a three-tier system comprised of Sub-Centres, primary health centres and community health centers. Through these centers, RNTCP (Revised National TB Control Program) has been implemented to manage TB in India (49) and the Tertiary Cancer Center (TCC) has been implemented for cancer care (50). These rural health centers operate through traditional methods, where patients need to visit the center to obtain care. To manage monitoring of relapse of TB and cancer requires consistent monitoring and follow up appointments even after successful therapy. The traditional health care system in the rural area are not suitable for such services that require prolong monitoring and frequent visits. In this context telemedicine could be the best rural public health approach (10). Telemedicine was identified and implemented by the WHO in 2005 (32), yet before Covid-19 imposed a worldwide lockdown, the telemedicine health approach was not widely accepted (33). As the telemedicine health approach is now rapidly becoming a global phenomenon, if put into widespread use for rural communities, it could potentially serve to alleviate the health disparities currently seen between rural and urban populations in developing nations.

The impact of IKS based healing method can be understood by the history of inoculation and vaccine as a means to combat epidemic in the ancient culture of rural India and China. For example, in ancient India and China, body-fluid based inoculation was practiced to combat smallpox (22). Ancient Kamarupa also practiced aerosol-based inoculation against smallpox (Chapter 5.6, pages 222-231, Reference 1). These IKS-based public health approaches may have encouraged the idea of vaccine development against the virus (22), an example of cultural philosophy converging with modern science to create effective solutions.

Another example of the adaptation or cultural appropriation of IKS based healing method is the Avatar Therapy, a Digital Therapeutics (DTx) interventions driven by software programs to treat medical

conditions. AvatarTherapy depends on a software-guided Avatar (digital version of oneself that enhances self-care). The idea of this Avatar stems from the Avatar Kosha of the Hindu IKS (1,14,23,39). Interestingly, in the tantric healing system of ancient Kamarupa, Avatar Kosha was symbolized by the amarnath (plant), meaning "king of immortality" (Introduction, page 12, Reference 23). Thus, using IKS-based public health approaches in developing innovative scientific hypotheses and experimental approaches will help to resolve upcoming challenges in medical science by creating novel ideas and technologies (24). As demonstrated by KTC, the IKS-based public health approach (51) can be combined with rural telemedicine (52) to further develop an improved and easily accessible rural public health approach as demonstrated by us (Figure 4-7). Our rural telemedicine program integrates an ancient public health approach, the Vedic Altruism based community medical care, with modern medicine and prepare to evolve as a modern digital therapeutic tool (42).

A summary of our IKS related work from 1994 to 2021 is as follows: we first used the temple complex network to complete our 15-year-long tuberculosis contact investigation study (Figure 1-3, and Supplementary note, Ref 4). Next, we extended the Vedic Altruism based telemedicine network to Arunachal Pradesh, which enabled us to complete a Gates Foundation-funded project on tuberculosis (5) as well as a cancer rehabilitation project (6), and a clinical study (7). Finally, we used the Vedic Altruism based telemedicine approach to manage stage I and stage II Covid-19 cases in the rural north Kamrup area of Assam from May 2020 to September 2021. The Nigudah Yoga Care done by the villagers showed significant effectiveness in reducing the odds of progression of stage IIa to stage IIb/III in Covid-19. All of these intricate, sometimes decades-long studies encompassing results of TB, cancer, and Covid-19 patients suggest the potential effectiveness of the Vedic Altruism based telemedicine in managing rural public health. As such, we propose that this indigenous knowledge system based bio-social medicine approach known as either Vedic Altruism or JUT be used as a template for developing telemedicine care in rural India as well as the greater India of Indo Pacific region (56). Such an effort may also provide us with reviving the muga silk tradition and economy (57), as well as understanding the Hindu Knowledge system, and its past, present and future contribution in the cultural emergence process (14) of Indo-Pacific that stretch from Kashgar in Central Asia to Angkor Wat in South East Asia (58). Importantly, these efforts may help us to combat the growing menace of TB as per Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation in May 2009 (59).

The limitations of our IKS based rural telemedicine research is largely due to its focus on the niche IKS of a rural community (Sualkuchi) in India. Mainly, its studies only encompass the people and philosophies of this area and thus, the sample sizes of the study groups are not significantly large, and there is not enough diversity to make widespread claims about the nature of all rural communities. Additionally, there are no comparable recognized studies, as the main ideas discussed are from a nearly extinct ancient knowledge

system. This study is therefore preliminary and requires further investigation in other rural communities of developing nations to corroborate its findings.

On the other hand the telemedicine in the Sualkchi Hajo cultural complex area has enabled us gain insight on Indian knowledge system, and its social networking structure as well as recovering the ancient philosophy of public health. Our ongoing work on Indigenous Kamarupa INformation Network (IKIN) may provide novel historical perspective on ancient trade and cultural exchanges as well as public health approaches of nearly 5000 years of Hindu civilization as discussed below.

5.0 Potential relevance of Vedic altruism in the study of Humanities and Social Sciences

We speculate the deep root of the IKIN in the ancient trade link of ancient Kamarupa with Indus Valley civilization, and the Vratya culture of North India (Chapter Searching in the relics of Indus Valley civilization for the root of JUT; 5.6.1 Vratya culture in kamarupa: the probable seed of JUT, and 5.6.2 The potential survival of the Vratya culture in the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex area, pages 215-228, Ref 1). Interestingly, member of IKIN used muga silk extensively for various purposes including the "muga tabiz", beads of copper connected by reeling muga silk thread (Figure 2). Such copper bead with muga silk has been excavated in an 2500 BC Indus Valley site (53) suggesting a potential trade link between ancient North Eastern South Asia, and Indus Valley (54). Moreover, some geometric symbols of Indus valley (Figure 3A, and Ref. 55) have similarities with tantric yantra of JUThealers (1,2). Thus, our work on JUT is taking us deeper in to the ancient history of human civilizations and their efforts in healing. Hence, Walden pond campus of the Thoreau Lab for Global Health, MA is actively pursuing research on the potential evidence of JUT in Indus Valley civilization with the collaboration with Harappa Archaeological Research Project (HARP) of Harvard University. Therefore, we are working on preserving the archaeological sites of JUT including the Suad Muni ashram area (Figure 2, 57) by submitting a project plan of preservation in 2021, and also a project plan for Muga silk revival in 2017, and a herbal garden plus cikitsha-satra network plan in 2014. By submitting these proposals we are also studying the interaction between IKS-based organization and India's government structure as per a longitudinal study on Hindu knowledge system as detailed elsewhere (39).

Thus, our study on Vedic altruism and its underlying philosophy as well as two decades of field study and the results as described in the text may also provide novel idea related to management theories, specially the interpretation of Elton May's human relations management theory that highlight the individual and group dynamics. We speculate that managers motivation and skill to facilitate Avatar Kosha in an organization may provide the best effective way to complete a given mission of an organization (Chapter 4, Ref.1), and therefore may contribute in international development as well as our efforts in biosphere protection (Chapter 2, Ref. 1). In this context, success or failure of an organization or government may be viewed as per the Vedic altruism

based social construct. As per JUT, social structure is an illusion (Maya) having Sahasa-ojash shakti that organize complex reality as a Jala or net of Dharma (Indra Jala or Indra's net). The asat-nigudah jala or bad-nigudah net is kind of social construction of complex reality that can create a destructive patch of virtual reality (Kala ojash as per Vedic altruism) (43), where Jiva Upakar or biological altruism can turn into Asura Kosha, or selfish ego. In this concept, while pursuing the healing process, the Avatar Kosha does not disappear following the completion of the task, but fuel the growth of the dark passion of Mana and Vigyana kosha. Thus the healing passion of altruism can turn into evil (36,43). Further research is necessary to integrate this Vedic altruism based social construct of reality with that of problem of evil, the theological question now that haunts medical ethics in the era of AI and genome editing (63).

Since the introduction of the term altruism by Auguste Comte, evolutionary psychologists, evolutionary biologists and ethologists have been debating about the basis of social as well as biological altruism. There is little consensus on altruism, although biological altruism has been explained in terms of group or kin selection, and anthropologists reported the phenomena of altruistic behavior among humans, while Edward Wilson reported altruism among ants in his groundbreaking book of 1975, *Sociobiology* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sociobiology:_The_New_Synthesis). Vedic altruism introduces another dimension to the phenomena of altruism i.e. the pre-condition that the altruistic agent need to reprogram to a higher state of power first, and then sacrifice that power for group fitness (1,9,41). This notion of reprogramming to a higher state of power also makes such altruistic activity prone to misuse of power, a path to loss of homeostasis. We have used the metaphysics of Vedic altruism to design scientific experiments to test the transformation of altruistic stem cells to cancer stem cells (60-62), as well as provide biographical explanation of evil (43). A similar metaphysical explanation was given to describe often harmful results of modern public health systems that fail to provide support for rural people who need them the most (1), as well as potential harmful effect of transhumanism (63).

Therefore, studying the underlying metaphysics of Vedic altruism or JUT may provide new insight into different problems that now confront the globalized world. In this context, a Gandhian social worker and senior co-author of this work, H.B. emphasized the poetic side of the philosophy of Vedic altruism as the Tantra of humanity (Manavatar Tantra) while delivering a public lecture in the 2019 annual meeting of Assam Literary Society (Axom Sahitya Sabha), and he explained the poem composed by his philosopher poet friend Krishna Ram Das (KRD) in 1994 (64). KRD, in his speech on Vedic Altruism (36) talked about the karya-karana (cause and effect) that connect the various components of pancha-kosha, including the biosphere and plant kingdom all interwoven in a co-operative relationship as per Madhu Vidya hypothesis of Earth Defense (Figure 11, Chapter 2.7, page 88 of Ref 1). Future research is required to find how such views of interdependence so

characteristic of Indian thought (65) may have influenced Thoreau, and Emerson to formulate the American transcendental philosophy (66), and its possible policy making application in the era of climate change.

6.0 Future Direction: modeling a Vedic altruism based global health theory

One of our key future research programs is to study whether the Avatar Kosha-based social group therapy could be understood in terms of evolutionary medicine (Chapter 2.9, page 89, and 4.10, page 174 of Ref. 1) and social evolution. Our lab has been interested in the evolutionary aspect of dietary supplements such as squalene on social evolution (Pages 11-14 of Ref. 23). Indeed, we traced several war legends of ancient tribal groups of Scandinavia, Japan, Central America, and the Mediterranean as well as India using squalene-rich herbs and plants such as Amaranth and Olive plants (Pages 11-14 of Ref. 23). We also noted that the symbol of Avatar Kosha for tantric healers was the squalene-rich plant, Amaranth (page 12 of Ref. 23). Did the squalene-rich diet or plant enhance the fitness of social groups such as the IKIN of the Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex? This question could be addressed by approaching IKIN as a social group capable of solving social dilemmas and, therefore, subject to structural and cultural selection as per multi-level selection theory (67). Thus, the structure of the Avatar Kosha-based altruism may be studied in terms of multi-level selection theory as an ongoing process of selection. The action of good *nigudah* can be considered altruistic as it enhances the group fitness by sacrificing the self-fitness of Avatar Kosha. Likewise, the action of Avatar Kosha in enhancing the group fitness of Pancha-kosha within the individual can be considered altruistic. It may be noted here that altruism is defined per evolutionary biology in terms of fitness effects, without reference to how individuals feel or think. A behavior or action is altruistic if it enhances the fitness of the group relative to other groups in a given social structure (page 235, Ref. 67). Therefore, future studies are required to analyze the altruistic aspect of Avatar kosha as per the multi-level selection theory. However, a question arises about whether Avatar Kosha promotes altruistic behavior or reciprocal cooperation. A thorough analysis of the altruistic aspect of Vedic altruism in terms of group selection theory is underway as we are adopting a mouse model of cooperation (68) to study the role of group fitness in squalene-mediated selective cytoprotection of stem cells versus cancer cells (page 81, Ref.23) in a model of platinum induced toxicity (69).

An alternative way to approach the study of Avatar kosha-based social group therapy is the process of self-organization and Emergence, an emerging area of research in evolutionary biology and medicine. Self-organization and Emergence are inherent properties of living beings, including metabolism (Chapter 11, *Metabolic Stress and Chaos*, pages 135-144, Ref. 23), and may guide natural selection (70). To explain the survival of Indigenous culture through invasion and colonialism, we proposed a model of social regeneration through cultural Emergence (14). In this model, the social network of knowledge generation remains dormant and then activated during social stress or dilemma through interaction and cooperation. This networking process then self-organizes the group into a state of Cultural Emergence for appropriate adaptation to the stressful environment. Thus, the

Emergence of Avatar Kosha in the IKIN may be considered a process of cultural emergence. Accordingly, Sahasa-ojash can be considered a network force that transforms random social networks into scale-free networks facilitating self-organization (Figure 8-9). Our ongoing prospective study of IKIN based TB control program (42) will provide us with enough data to test this hypothesis. A positive finding may indicate that Vedic altruism may enhance social regeneration through self-organization of the biosocial healing process dormant in our society/culture and the entire ecosystem as per the Madhu-Vidya component of Vedic altruism (36).

Figure 8: Social network analysis of IKIN during covid19 study (Figure 6C) provided us that IKIN as a scale-free network, where Hatisatra emerged as a bridging HUB between ancient knowledge practiced in Hatisatra, and modern social network of IKIN (42). This bridging HUB network could be considered as the “beam of knowledge” in the social theory of regeneration based through cultural emergence (14). Our ongoing prospective study on TB control program will provide further research to develop this theory of social regeneration, and therefore may contribute in developing a novel theory on global health.

Yet another way to study Avatar Kosha-based group therapy is to revisit several social theories in healthcare, including the social theory of unintended consequence, social reconstruction of reality, theory of social suffering, and the theory of bipower (71-73). As we proceed with our practical and factual research on the Vedic altruism-based telemedicine approach to global health issues such as tuberculosis and cancer, our research may also help develop a novel theory. Thus, one of the key future directions of our research on Vedic altruism is to find a comprehensive social medicine theory on global health (41) that may provide a basis for policy-making for the better management of future global pandemics as well as climate change and globalization related public health disparities and distress.

7.0 Future Direction: Modeling a Vedic Altruism-Based Stem Cell Niche Defense

To meet the complex challenges of the twenty-first century, science requires not only technological advancement but also philosophical insight. However, modern scientists, particularly biomedical scientists, rarely seek philosophical guidance to generate conceptual frameworks or formulate new theories in basic science and public health. In this context, the Indian Knowledge System (IKS) may play an important role, as it is enriched by deep philosophical traditions that can stimulate new ways of thinking about life, disease, healing, and collective resilience.

We and others have applied philosophical ontology to gain insight into stem-cell biology, particularly the concept of stemness, which refers to the identity, state, and functional potential of a stem cell. In this process, the **Panchapadika education system** may be viewed as an important pedagogical foundation. We define Panchapadika as a five-step educational approach through which observation, reflection, dialogue, reasoning, and experiential validation are integrated to generate knowledge. Such an approach allows philosophical concepts to be transformed into scientific questions, hypotheses, and experimental models. One of the important component of this Shruada education system of the Muga silk weavers and the artisan communities of Hajo-Sualkuchi cultural complex is the Satavata Tarka. Here, **Satavata Tarka** (Figure 10) refers to a JUT-based dialectic and suppositional reasoning method in which apparently opposing ideas are brought into structured dialogue to generate new insight, or **Prajna Agan**. In our work, this method helped transform metaphysical concepts such as good-nigudah, Avatar Kosha, and Vedic Altruism into scientifically testable hypotheses in stem-cell biology, host–pathogen interaction, and global health (Figure 9-10). Importantly, by implementing the Vedic philosophical concepts of **Avatarvada**, we gained conceptual insight into stem-cell altruism and stem-cell niche defense as well as into global health challenges such as tuberculosis and COVID-19. Notably, applications of Vedic Altruism in our laboratory provide examples of how IKS-based philosophical concepts can be translated into experimentally testable scientific models. We have studied the pathogen-induced apoptotic cell death as a simple biological model of Adaptive Altruism, where an infected cell undergoes programmed death to limit pathogen replication and protect the larger tissue or host. Upon infection, a host cell may activate stress-response pathways that culminate in apoptotic cell death. Although this leads to the loss of the infected individual cell, the process may restrict intracellular pathogen replication, reduce spread to neighboring cells, and protect the larger tissue or host organism. In this sense, pathogen-induced apoptosis can be viewed as a form of adaptive or altruistic cell death, where sacrifice at one level contributes to protection at a higher level of biological organization. This concept provides a modern biological parallel to the JUT idea that, during stress, a higher protective state emerges to preserve the larger whole. We have used the finding to further sharpen our two decades old idea of stem-cell niche defense, where stress-induced stem or stromal cell states may act protectively to preserve tissue integrity, regulate host–pathogen interaction, or oppose malignant transformation. Together, these examples suggest that Vedic Altruism can serve not merely as a cultural or metaphysical framework, but also as a source of scientific hypothesis generation for stem-cell biology, evolutionary medicine, and global health science.

Figure 9: Application of Vedic Altruism in public health science

A. The Sualkuchi-Hajo-Kamakhya cultural complex along the ancient Vedic Silk Road.

It seems that pre-Vedic and Vedic culture spread from North West India to North East India via Kashmir and Tibet along this silk route. Therefore, it can be termed as the "Vedic Silk Road." Evidence for its existence includes the Kalita tribe of Kamrup and their Vedic culture, Muga silk culture of Sualkuchi, and the Vedic Tantra philosophy of Kamarupa, Tibet, Kashmir, and South East Asia.

The Vedic Silk road starts at Kushi of Central Asia and ends at Angkor Wat of Cambodia, the largest Vishnu temple in the world constructed in 6th century, contemporary to Hayagriva Vishnu temple of Kamrup/India. Detailed research is described in the book "Akjon Bigvanir Hindutva Yatra" (Hindutva Journey of a Scientist, Dr. Bikul Das, 2018, page 510).

B. The concept of Avatar Kosha based community healing in the ancient temple complexes of Sualkuchi-Hajo-Kamakhya cultural complex

Vedic altruism is a mind-body-based bio-social medicine approach based on "Avatar Kosha", which, according to Vedic Altruism, is a transient kosha of the Pancha kosha system.

Avatar Kosha is altruistic, as it enhances the group fitness while sacrificing self-fitness. The local Qash of rural Kamrupa organized a network of Xasang (local temple) based healing systems to activate Avatar Kosha in the entire community during epidemic such as smallpox and cholera.

Figure 10: The application of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra (Vedic Altruism) based suppositional reasoning (Satvata tarka) in formulating scientific hypothesis, and experimental designs in our research at KaviKrishna lab.

A. The Guru Asana Vyuh

- 1-2. Observation of a desire (ichha-prataskhya)
3. Inference based on priori knowledge (satvata/purvavat-anuman)
4. Suppositional reasoning (yukti-tarka)
5. Special feature of doubt (samasya-laksana)
6. Examination of a new idea (parkisa-dharana)
7. Knowledge-Emergence (Prajna-agan.

component of Satvata Tarka. The dynamic interaction between two distinct ideas (Dharana) leads to Satvata sanjog or Nadi (realistic connection) that enables knowledge emergence (Prajna Agan). B. The seven steps of Satvata tarka.

C.

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.11.14.382572v1>

Experimental plan to identify extracellular vesicles in aerosol of smear negative pulmonary TB subjects based on the Satvata Tarka method of Vedic Jiva Upakara Tantra (Vedic Altruism).

D. News report in Assam Tribune about the design of scientific experiments based on Vedic altruism, November 18, 2020

8.0 Conclusions:

Bring the old abstract here...

The convergence of the ideas behind traditional methods of medical care and modern medical and scientific practices can lead to effective, novel approaches to public health. Vedic altruism, or JUT, is a prime example of an IKS-based approach that, when implemented in modern rural communities, allows for productive collaboration between doctors and patients. The practice of integrating the two systems of thought results in favorable outcomes for both parties: the rural community is able to preserve their cultural identity whilst adapting to the modern world, and the medical practitioners are challenged to think beyond their immediate knowledge of science, allowing the production of new ideas, or, knowledge emergence, to occur. In Kamrup, Assam, the public health approach run by the tantric practitioners based on Avatar Kosha and Sahasa-ojash led to the scientific findings of Mtb antigens and the establishment of KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care, a telemedicine practice that seeks to use a bio-social understanding of medicine to help treat its patients and investigate the nature of TB, Covid-19, cancer, and the cancer health disparity. Thus, scientific exploration and interaction with the IKS of rural communities should be adopted throughout developing nations, such as India, in order to ameliorate rural health care and discover novel ways of viewing scientific research.

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B.D. initiated and B.D. and H.B. conceptualized the metaphysics, whereas B.D., T.B. and L.P. initiated various research projects mentioned in the book. B.D., T.B., L.P., R.D., S.B., P.S., S.M., N.R.D. and

T.D. performed the clinical work mentioned in Figures 6-7. T.B. and L.P. contributed in designing the sahasa-
ojash score (Fig. 5). T.B. wrote the first draft. R.D. wrote the philosophical part of the text and contributed to
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10. Table 2: Glossary:

Avatar: “descent”; the essence of a deity in another form. Often associated with Vishnu, the Hindu God (Saguna Brahman) of preservation or maintenance of the Universe.

Avatar Kosha: a latent layer of the mind-body (or community) that arises only during times of stress, unlike the five *koshas* of the Pancha Kosha system, which are always active. It takes on a powerful and governing role to return the mind-body (or community) to homeostasis

Ayurveda: “Ayur” = life, “Veda” = science; an ancient Indian system of wholistic medicine that aims to achieve a balance between the mind, body, and spirit

Ckitisha Satra: temple-hospital

Hatisatra Namghar: prayer house located in Hatisatra

Idu-Mishimi: tribe living in Roing, Arunachal Pradesh who volunteered to be patients

Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS): a knowledge system created and maintained by an indigenous culture over many generations and thus, is adaptable to its environment

Jagat Ghora (JG): the tantric healer whose TB patients were treated with JUT based approach

Jiva: living being/life force

KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care (KTC): our telemedicine care clinic that performs all the studies

Kirtan Yoga: “chanting” in Sanskrit, one of the traditional yoga practices

Krimis: microscopic worms akin to metaphysical creatures mentioned in ancient Hindu

texts

Kosha: a covering, or layer, of the *Atman* (Self). Directly translated as “sheath” in Sanskrit

Nadi: on an individual level: energy network of a body; on a communal level: network of community collaboration

Nigudah (nigoda): microscopic life according to Jain philosophy. Meaning is similar to *krimis*

Good-Nigudah: microscopic life that does good to help our pancha kosha

Bad-Nigudah: invisible microscopic life that do bad to harm our pancha kosha

Nigudah Yoga Pranayama: a specific type of yoga with an emphasis on breathing

Ojash: spiritual energy; widely referred to as ‘ojas’

Ojhas: local practitioners of tantric medicine

Pancha Kosha System: consists of the five layers of being (Anna, Prana, Mana, Vigyan, and Ananda kosha) that surround the *Atman* (Self)

Sahaja Jiva Ojas: the innate bio-energy of a patient’s body

Sahasa-Ojash: a mind-body healing effect that arises due to a bio-social healing combination of crude vaccination, herbal nutrition, tantric rituals, and kirtan yoga

Satvata tarka: dialectic method of reasoning

Svatantra Kshetra: independent, higher form of *Vidhata Kshetra*

Sualkuchi-Hajo: Sualkuchi is a village, located in the Hajo subdivision of the Kamrup district of Assam

Tantra: any systematic broadly applicable text or theory of esoteric Hindu tradition

Tarka: suppositional reasoning

Upakara: altruism

Veda/Vedas: all the sacred Hindu texts; the four most important are the Rig-Veda, Atharva-Veda, Sama-Veda, and Yajur-Veda

Vedic Altruism/JUT: a traditional medical philosophy of the ancient Sualkuchi-Hajo area that is centered around the idea of the emergence of an *Avatar Kosha* within an individual’s mind-body (or within a community) during times of high stress

Vidhata Kshetra: interactive field of people/assembly, the Avatar of *Vidhata-Ojash*

Vidhata-Ojash: putative altruistic social defense mechanism

Vyadhikshyamatra: body's immune system

Yantra: a complex, geometric healer's instrument

11. Abbreviation list:

1. IKS: Indigenous Knowledge System
2. COPD: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
3. TB: Tuberculosis
4. PTB: Pulmonary Tuberculosis
5. KTC: KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care
6. IKIN: indigenous Kamarupa information network
7. JUT: Jiva Upakara Tantra
8. JG: Jagat Ghora
9. FGD: Focused Group Discussion
10. DKB: Dayal Krishna Bora
11. EV: Extracellular Vesicles
12. HRQOL: Health-related quality of life
13. MSCs: Mesenchymal Stem Cells
14. DOTS: Directly Observed Therapy Short Course
15. BM: Bone Marrow
16. HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus
17. AFB: Acid Fast Bacillus
18. DOT: Directly Observed Therapy
19. DNA: Deoxyribonucleic acid
20. MTB: Mycobacterium tuberculosis
21. DBT: Department of Biotechnology
22. MDR-TB: Multidrug-resistant TB
23. WGS: Whole Genome Sequencing
24. ICMR: Indian Council of Medical Research
25. BHT: Breath-Holding Test
26. UPK: Undisclosed Public Knowledge
27. RNTCP: Revised National TB Control Program
28. TCC: Tertiary Cancer Center
29. WHO: World Health Organisation
30. DTx: Digital Therapeutics
31. HARP: Harappa Archaeological Research Project
32. KKL: KaviKrishna Laboratory

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